

ALGORITHM FOR CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL OPTION FOR ENDOPROSTHETICS FOR DYSPLASTIC COXARTHROSIS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10081248>

Introduction. The most accurate installation of endoprosthesis components with orientation to the anatomical axis of the limb, which can eliminate during endoprosthetics coxavar or coxavalga with full compensation of ante- or retroversion angles, and reduction to the correct rotation angle, is the main and most difficult task of preoperative planning [1-5].

The aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm for determining the rimming point and choosing the optimal endoprosthetics option.

The research material was 52 patients operated on using the proposed technique for the period from 2015 to 2021. The proposed algorithm took into account the anatomical and functional state of the hip joint, the degree of dysplasia and the angle between the planar anatomical formations. For comparison

Results. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithm was assessed at a three-month follow-up using the Harris rating scale. At the same time, it was possible to improve performance in the following evaluation criteria:

- reduce pain (by 11.3%)
- functional results (16.8%)
- range of motion in the joint (15.2%)

Conclusion. The proposed algorithm, which takes into account the anatomical and functional state of the hip joint, the degree of dysplasia and the angle between planar anatomical formations, allows improving the results of endoprosthetics for dysplastic coxarthrosis by an average of 13.7% and speed up the time for dynamization and rehabilitation of patients.

References:

1. Jakobsen SS, Overgaard S, Søballe K, Ovesen O, Mygind-Klavsen B, Dippmann CA, Jensen MU, Stürup J, Retpen J. The interface between periacetabular osteotomy, hip arthroscopy and total hip arthroplasty in the young adult hip. EFORT OpenRev. 2018 Jul 11;3(7):408-417.

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2. Gaffney B.M., Hillen T.J., Nepple J.J., Clohisy J.C., Harris M.D., Statistical Shape Modeling of Femur Shape Variability in Female Patients with Hip Dysplasia // J Orthop Res. 2019 Jan 17. doi: 10.1002/jor.24214.
3. Todhunter R.J., Garrison S.J., Jordan J., Hunter L., Castelhana MG. Gene expression in hip soft tissues in incipient canine hip dysplasia and osteoarthritis. // J Orthop Res. 2018 Nov 19. doi: 10.1002/jor.24178.
4. Yin S., Zhong H. Effectiveness of autologous femoral head bone graft in total hip arthroplasty for Crowe type III developmental dysplasia of hip with acetabular bone defect. Zhongguo Xiu Fu Chong Jian Wai Ke Za Zhi. 2018. V. 32(1). P. 20-24. DOI: 10.7507/1002-1892.201708005.
5. Ziran N., Varcadipane J., Kadri O., Ussef N., Kanim L., Foster A., Matta J. Ten- and 20-year Survivorship of the Hip After Periacetabular Osteotomy for Acetabular Dysplasia. // J Am Acad Orthop Surg. 2018 Nov 14. doi: 10.5435/JAAOS-D-17-00810.

